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Effect Of Cashless Economy On Micro And Small-Scale Business In Abuja, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

A Cashless Economy can be likened to a financial system that minimizes the use of physical cash through the provision of alternative means of making payments. This study set out to examine the effect of a cashless policy on the survival of small and micro-scale businesses in Abuja, Nigeria. Some of the objectives of the study were to evaluate the factors that impede the adaptation of the cashless policy in Abuja. The study was carried out through the administration of a questionnaire to both the owners and operators of small businesses in the study area. The findings revealed that there are conveniences in electronic transactions, particularly POS, ATM, Mobile banking, and Automatic electronic payments assist banks in making deposits and by extension providing the needed funds to be loaned to small businesses. The study recommended, amongst others, that the government should embark on viable reforms that will increase the viability of small-scale businesses in Nigeria.

Keywords: Cashless, Economy, Micro, Small scale, Business

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The concept of small and medium-scale enterprises is not new to the Nigerian business system. A huge body of extant literature consistently agrees with the fact that small and medium scale enterprises tend to improve the economy of any nation through job creation “Udensi, Igbara, Paago and Chieke (2014), Daisi (2012), Nelson and Nelson (2010), Gboski, Joshua and Stephen (2007) cited in Okeke (2017). The Monetary Systems as we all understand them today began with the barter system, which metamorphosed into broad markets. This marketing system was mainly characterized by the exchange of goods for goods. Monetary policy, according to Elechi & Rufus (2016), has been a tool for economic management to bring sustainable growth and development. Moreover, Okeke (2017) emphasized that the recent monetary policies emanating from the Nigeria Apex Bank and the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) had both negative and positive effects on different sectors of the economy. For instance, the recent introduction of the cashless policy by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) has affected small and medium-scale enterprises to the point where it has been described by economic watchers as declining in its glory. This is evident in the performance of small and medium-scale enterprises ‘ operations and growth, especially in the rural areas of the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.

A cashless economy is an environment in which money is spent without being physically carried from one place to another. This process works with electronic devices as a means of information that explains how much an individual has deposited (Ikphelan and Ehimare, 2012). Moreover, information technology has an important role to play in the growth and development of any nation. Information technology

processes in the communication of data. These include but are not limited to Automatic Teller machines and networking to facilitate access to the accounts of depositors from any branch of the bank. According to the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN, 2011) in Okeke (2017), the cashless policy was conceptualized by Nigeria's Apex Bank to move the Nigerian economy from cash-based to cashless through the introduction of various electronic payment systems. A major reason for the introduction of the cashless monetary policy was to be in line with its contemporaries in other countries and or discourage the mass movement of cash manually. The policy was also meant to improve the proficiency of the Nigerian payment system thus improving the quality of service delivery by the Nigerian banking system. The cashless policy was further meant to curb the risk associated with the movement of cash, including the high cost of carrying cash, the high risk of using cash, the informal economy, inefficiency, high subsidy, and corruption (CNB, 2011).

In the view of David (2012), Nigeria did not embrace electronic banking as when its contemporary in the developed world did. Historically, different forms of payment systems have existed. For instance, trade by barter was the informal means of transaction in vogue before the invention of money as a legal tender. However, the introduction of money came with its attendant disadvantages among which include double coincidence and others. Since Nigeria gained independence in 1960, the country has evolved via diverse constitutional reforms, banking policies, and economic policies mainly aimed at achieving developmental goals and enhancing social welfare. However, despite all these reforms, there has been no substantial change in Nigerian human development indices. According to the Central Bank of Nigeria (2022), the new cashless policy was introduced for several reasons, including to drive the development and modernization of our payment system. Enhance the acceptance and usage of the recently introduced e-Naira by the Central Bank of Nigeria. Researchers in Economics and Finance have noted that an efficient and modern payment system is positively linked to economic development and growth and is a key enabler of the survival of small and medium-scale enterprises. Furthermore, the cashless policy was aimed at reducing the cost of credit, driving, and increasing financial inclusion, especially among rural dwellers, through the provision of more efficient transaction options. Moreover, the cashless policy aims at curbing some of the negative consequences associated with the high usage of cash in the economy, including the high cost of carrying cash, and the high risk of using cash (CBN 2022).

It is against this backdrop that this study seeks to analyze the effects of cashless policy implementation on the survival of small and medium-scale enterprises in Abuja, Nigeria.

1.2 Statement of the problem

The problem of this study is to investigate the effect of the implementation of the cashless policy on the survival of small and medium-scale enterprises in Nigeria with a focus on Abuja.

The 2012 financial service survey revealed that the small, and medium scale enterprises had limited adoption of electronic payment and services. The data gathered revealed that only 0.7% of banked adults use POS terminals, 0.8% of banked adults use the Internet, and less than 2.5% use mobile phones for banking transactions.

Echekoba and Ezu (2012) carried out a study in Nigeria. The study revealed that 68.2% of the respondents complained about staying long in the queues in the banks, 28.9% were unsatisfied with the attitudes of bank teller officers (known as Cashier), and about 2.89% were not satisfied with the location of the banking halls. Similarly, James (2012) accessed the acceptance of e-banking in Nigeria. The findings revealed that the acceptance of e-banking in Nigeria was significantly affected by age, educational background, income, perceived benefits, ease of use, perceived risk, and enjoyment. For Small businesses, carrying large sums of cash can be risky, making both the seller and the buyer vulnerable to theft or robbery. It has also been discovered that cash transactions do not offer the same level of protection to small businesses as other forms of payment, such as credit cards or online payment systems (Merg, 2023). Merg (2023), further asserts that cash transactions do not leave a clear trail of the transaction, making it challenging to keep track of the payments made. This is capable of creating difficulties for small businesses when it comes to accounting and record keeping.

The purpose of this study is to examine all possible ways that a cashless economy affects the survival rate of micro and small-scale Business entities in Abuja, Nigeria. It also aims at identifying specific problems or challenges facing these small-scale businesses and firms when it comes to adopting mobile banking and the use of other electronic banking procedures like Automated Teller Machine (ATM) point of sales terminals (POS), GSM in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.

1.3 Objectives of the study

The objectives of this study include:

- i. To examine the effect of a cashless economy on the performance of small and medium-scale businesses in Abuja.
- ii. Evaluate the challenges that hindered the effective adoption of a cashless economy by small and medium-scale businesses in Abuja.
- iii. To ascertain if a cashless economy in any way contributes to the growth (survival) of small and medium-scale businesses in Abuja.
- iv. Examine the way forward to curbing the challenges associated with cashless economy policy adoption in Abuja.

1.4 Research Questions

- i. Does the adoption of a cashless economy have any effect on the performance of small and medium-scale businesses in Abuja?
- ii. What are the challenges that have hindered the adoption of the cashless economy policy in Abuja?
- iii. To what extent does a cashless economy contribute to the growth/survival of small and medium-scale businesses in Abuja?
- iv. What is the way forward to curbing the challenges associated with the adoption of a cashless economy in Abuja?

2.0. Review of Literature

2.1. Concept of a Cashless Economy

The original definition of money connotes that money plays three vital roles. These are (i) a unit of account, (ii) a medium of exchange, and (iii) a store of value.

However, in a cashless economy, money does not operate as a store of value. In the view of Fermer (2004), a cashless economy does not refer to the outright absence of cash transactions in the economic setting but one in which the amount of cash-based transactions is kept at a minimum and monitored. As noted by Okeke (2017), a cashless economy is an environment in which money is spent without being physically carried from one point to another. Moreso, cashless systems use electronic devices as a means of information that reveal how much a person has deposited and or withdrawn from his or her bank account. A cashless economy, in the view of Adewale (2012), simply illustrates a gradual or radical movement of the entire payment system of an economy from the use of physical cash to a systemic adoption of other nonphysical cash modes of payment in the commercial and personal. Local and international trade both in public and private life within a given economy.

In a cashless economy, the use of non-cash payment methods such as cards (credit and debit) dominates the use of cash in payments. The card-based payment system has several players. These include the providers of card-based payment systems, some of which are the card forms such as Master Card and Visa, which provide their payment network for the systems to function. The other set of providers are the banks that act as acquires from merchants and issuers for cardholders and reach the card payment services to the ultimate users. It is imperative to note that the card payment system is an income-generating initiative for both providers.

2.1.1. Prospects of a cashless policy in Nigeria

For many centuries, cash has played a major role in daily commerce. It has been known to help ordinary people exchange their products and labor for the goods and services they require without stressful negotiations over exchanges. However, cash alternatives have gradually taken root in our economic body

polity. The increased use of electronic payment systems has been responsible for the growth of a cashless society (Humphrey and Berger, 1996; Onuley, 2016).

a) **Benefits of a cashless policy**

- For consumers [Increased convenience; reduced risk of cash-related crimes; more service options, cheaper access to banking services and access to credit]
- For companies [faster access to capital; reduced revenue leakage; and reduced cash handling costs]
- For Government [increased tax collections, greater financial inclusion, increased economic development]
- Reduce money laundering
- Check for terrorist financing
- Encourage financial deepening and promote savings
- Reduce overreliance on cash transactions
- Promote financial inclusion
- Effectiveness of monetary policy and
- Employment creation in the financial sector

b) **Challenges of cashless policy in Nigeria**

- **Lack of confidence:** One of the major challenges is the security issue in the development of the cashless policy.
- **Infrastructure:** Nigeria does not have adequate financial infrastructure to implement the cashless policy. These include inadequate ATM points of sales system, mobile banking, and other mediums that have to expand to reach at least 80% of the whole economy.
- **Power:** The state of power in Nigeria is discouraging. Thus, the available power cannot accommodate smooth operations of financial activities. There is an absolute need to develop a reliable and sustainable power supply.
- **Security:** In regards to laws that are needed to enforce new methods of transactions and a charging culture. The CBN must work and partner with the legislatures to ensure adequate legislation is formulated.
- **Behavioral Constraints:** The understanding that Nigeria is a cash-based society is a huge challenge.
- **Banks Attitudes:** Most banks in Nigeria are very conservative, they introduce very innovative products and marketing techniques to customers.
- **Low Level of Internet Penetration and weak telecommunication services** impede the smooth development and enhancement of e-payment services in Nigeria.

2.2. Concept of Micro and Small-Scale Business

According to Safiriyu and Njogo (2012), there is no universal definition of micro and small-scale enterprises as the changes in price level and advancement in technology affect their real definition. Carpenter (2003), identifies other criteria such as financial strength, relative size, sales value, initial capital outlay, and types of industry.

Therefore, micro and small-scale enterprises can assume a lot of meaning in different countries and at different times. In Nigeria, the definition of micro and small-scale enterprises has been on different criteria such as investment in machinery and equipment, working capital, capital cost, turnover, and values of installed fixed cost (Osotimelium, 2012). The National Council on Industry (1991) defined micro enterprises as an industry whose total project cost excluding the cost of land but including working capital is not more than five hundred thousand naira (N 500,000) while small-scale enterprises are those industries whose total project cost excluding the cost of land but including working capital does not exceed five million naira (N5, 000,000). National Council on Industry (1996) after a review defined micro enterprises as an industry whose total cost including working capital but excluding the cost of land is not

more than one million naira (N1, 000,000) with a labor size of not more than ten workers while small scale enterprises is an industry whose total cost including working capital but excluding the cost of land is over one-million (N1, 000,000).

Despite its definition, micro and small-scale businesses are generally referred to as the engine of growth in many economies and a major factor in promoting private sector development. Micro and small-scale enterprises not only contribute significantly to improved living standards, but they also bring about substantial local capital formation and achieve high levels of productivity and capability. Their importance according to Adebisi (2013) is viewed from the perspective of employment generation, contributions to export earnings, and gross domestic product (GDP). Oftentimes, they are the only source of employment in poor regions and rural areas, thereby playing an important role in poverty reduction in most developing countries. Adebisi (2013) further noted that micro and small-scale enterprises create competitive market pressure, while they also play important roles as sub-contractors in the downsizing, privatization, and restructuring of large enterprises.

Despite their relevance, micro and small-scale businesses easily collapse or fail. Different literatures have discussed the major reasons for their failure. Udechukwu (2003) highlighted some problems that militate against the effective operations of micro and small-scale businesses. These include poor policy implementation, lack of continuity, poor capital outlay, poor management expertise, inadequate information base, lack of raw materials, poor accounting systems, unstable policy environment, lack of market knowledge, lack of purpose and lack of financial planning, lack of patronage for locally produced goods by those in authority, lack of planning, inimical government rules and regulations, lack of technical know low and higher interest rate are other problems associated with the failure of micro and small scale enterprises in Nigeria (Ekpenyong & Nyong, 1992).

2.3. Theoretical framework

Theory of money

The underlying theory for this study is the theory of money. The theory of money has its roots in the 16th century during which classical economists such as Jean Bold at that time sought to understand the cause of the increase in French commodities prices. He concluded that, among other factors, the increase in gold and silver which served as means of exchange then were responsible for the rise in the demand of French-made goods and commodities, thus linking movements in price to movement in money stock. The theory of money was further advanced by John Locke in the 1690s to examine the effects of money on trade, the role of interest rates, and the demand for money in the economy (Omonukwue 2010). The role of money in particular as a medium of exchange to facilitate trade transactions was birthed. Most economists at that time posited that the amount of money needed for such transactions would depend on the velocity of money in circulation and the relationship between the demand and supply of money such that where there was excess demand over supply, interest rates rose and vice versa (Cantillon, 1755, Locke 1692) as cited in Okeke (2019). The theory of money has been described by different schools of thought in their different opinions. For instance, the monetarist is concerned with the explanation for the changes in price level. In their view, a stable and equilibrium relationship exists between the adjustments in the quantity of money and the price level. On the other hand, they disagree with the fact that there is any form of monetary influence on real output both in the short and long run. The less tough monetarists agree that money influences output in the short run, but only prices in the long run. The introduction of the modern banking system has to a great extent brought about the gradual elimination of cash-based economy in most jurisdictions. In Nigeria, for example, most banks have adopted this cashless policy, though with some pressing challenges (Okeke, 2017).

2.4. Empirical Review

Various empirical studies have been carried out on the effect of a cashless policy on the development of small and medium-scale enterprises in Nigeria. Okeke (2017) examined the effect of the cashless policy on the development of small and medium-scale enterprises in Anambra state. The study found that

automated teller machines (ATM) had a significant effect on the development of small and medium-scale enterprises in Anambra state. However, other cashless economy services medium such as mobile banking and internet banking had insignificant negative effects on the performance of small and medium scale enterprises in the state.

Adewoye (2013) studied the impact of mobile banking on service delivery in Nigerian commercial Banks through the use of a questionnaire. The study found that the introduction of e-banking services has improved banking efficiency in rendering services to customers. These findings showed that mobile banking improved banks' service delivery in the form of transactional conveniences, saving time, quick transaction alerts, and saving of service costs which has increased customer relationship and satisfaction.

Morufu and Taibat (2012) employed a qualitative survey to ascertain bankers' perceptions of electronic banking in Nigeria. The findings revealed that bankers in Nigeria perceive electronic banking as a tool for minimizing inconveniences, reducing transaction costs, altering customer's queuing patterns, and saving customers' banking time. Olorunsegun (2010) used cluster sampling techniques to study the impact of electronic banking in the Nigerian banking system. The study found that banks with effective electronic banking systems had improved efficiency and increased customer relationship and satisfaction. Olajide (2012) investigated cashless banking in Nigeria and its implications on the economy. Findings from the study reveal that cashless banking will boost the economy of the country in the long run.

James (2013) employed the Rogers Diffusion of innovation theory to investigate the determinants of the adoption of mobile banking in Nigeria. The study empirically revealed that age, educational qualification, relative advantage, complexity, compatibility, observeability, and triability were important determinants of the adoption of mobile banking. This therefore makes it imperative for relevant stakeholders to make efforts to positively influence these independent variables to make mobile banking more popular. Ezeoha (2006) employed a descriptive survey to examine regulating Internet banking in Nigeria, with its problems and challenges. The study found that Internet banking in Nigeria is slowly being embraced by customers because Internet practices in Nigeria have been abused by cyber fraudsters who use real and deceptive banking websites to fool users and assess their sensitive information and funds.

3.0. METHODOLOGY

A huge number of business entrepreneurs in the area of study had a formal understanding of the effect of a cashless economy on the performance of their businesses.

3.1. Population and Sampling

The population is the total number of persons, objects, or items from which the researcher could draw the study sample. The target population for this study was operators and owners of small and medium-scale enterprises in Abuja the Federal Capital Territory of Nigeria. This study also employed a survey research design to achieve the aim of the research.

3.2. Sampling Size Determinant

This study employed judgmental sampling, also called purposive sampling or authoritative sampling, which is a non-probability sampling technique in which the sample members are chosen only based on the researcher's knowledge and judgment. Because of this, the sample size was allocated according to the six local government councils in Abuja. Each Local Government Area had a sample size of 90, making it a total of 540 respondents.

Sampling process

Local Govt Councils	Urban/Rural Areas of Study	Number of Respondents
Abuja Municipal Area Council	Garki (Urban)	60
	Apo Village (Rural)	30
Gwagwalada Area Council	Gwagwalada Town (Urban)	60
	Dobi (Rural)	30
Bwari Area Council	Kubwa (Urban)	60
	Barapa (Rural)	30
Kuje Area Council	Kuje Town (Urban)	60
	Pasali (Rural)	30
Kwali Area Council	Kwali Town (Urban)	60
	Leleyi (Rural)	30
Abaji Area Council	Abaji Town (Urban)	60
	Agyana (Rural)	30
Total 6 LGAs	12 Communities/Towns	540

For this study, a survey design has been adopted to meet the purpose of the study. It is considered appropriate because it has the advantage of effectiveness in getting information about personal perceptions, feelings, and anticipation. The survey was carried out by the administration of questionnaires to both the owners and operators of small and medium-scale enterprises in the rural and urban centers of the Six Area Councils of the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. The data generated from this study were subjected to analysis using four (4) Likert scale types and simple percentages.

4.1. Data Analysis

Table 4.1 Responses to research question one.

S/N	Item	SA	A	SD	D	A%	D%
1.	ATM & Mobile Banking provide convenience in Banking	290	160	49	41	83.33	16.66
2.	It is easy to obtain credit for your Business	30	21	297	192	9.44	90.56
3.	Electronic Transactions increased the purchasing power of people	23	36	157	324	10.92	89.07
4.	As a result of Electronic Banking, bank deposits have increased in your area	215	235	33	57	83.33	16.66
5.	Is it convenient and safer to use Electronic payment Devices?	205	270	27	38	87.9	12.03
6.	There appears to be long procedure for cheque clearance	63	58	119	300	22.40	77.59
	TOTAL	836	780	682	952		

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Overall percentage

$$\text{Agree} = \frac{1,606}{3,240} \times 100 = 49.56\%$$

$$\text{Disagree} = \frac{1,634}{3,240} \times 100 = 50.43\%$$

Table 4.2 Responses to Research Question Two.

S/N	Item	SA	A	SD	D	A%	D%
1.	Has awareness and knowledge of cashless policy Adoption been properly made	43	47	200	250	16.66	83.33
2.	Do you have easy access to information communication Technology	51	36	251	252	16.11	93.14
3.	The majority of small-scale enterprises in Abuja have poor banking habit	281	191	38	30	87.44	12.59
4.	Most small and medium enterprises in Abuja carry out transactions on cash Basis	301	160	42	37	85.37	14.62
5.	There is no fear of online fraud in cashless transactions & unreliable network	10	19	315	196	5.37	94.62
6.	There is an improvement in power supply for smooth financial activities	37	21	201	281	10.74	89.25
7.	The literacy level is low, especially in Abuja	40	31	263	266	13.14	86.55
8.	There are too many protocols in cheque clearance leading to stale cheques	201	156	101	82	66.11	33.88
	Total	964	661	1,411	1,394		

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Overall percentage

$$\text{Agree} = \frac{1,625}{4,430} \times 100 = 36.68\%$$

$$\text{Disagree} = \frac{2,805}{4,430} \times \frac{100}{1} = 63.32\%$$

Table 4.3 Responses to Research Question Three.

S/N	Item	SA	A	SD	D	A%	D%
1.	Government support for small and medium-sized businesses makes them productive	351	181	-	-	100	0
2.	Enhancing the performance of small and medium will create employment opportunities	307	167	-	66	87.77	12.23
3.	Creating Awareness about Banking services and its benefits will boost the performance of SME's and Capital Base	251	156	83	50	75.37	24.63
	TOTAL	909	504	83	116		

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Overall percentage

$$\text{Agree} = \frac{1,413}{1,612} \times 100 = 87.65\%$$

$$\text{Disagree} = \frac{199}{1,612} \times 100 = 12.34\%$$

Table 4.4 Responses to research question four.

S/N	Item	SA	A	SD	D	A%	D%
1.	Creating more awareness will enhance the survival of SMEs in Nigeria	451	89	-	-	100	0
2.	Provision of efficient Network to Enhance Electronic Transfers.	392	148	-	-	100	0
3.	Make policies and Reforms to create credits for SMEs	371	169	-	-	100	0
4.	Creating more payment points like ATMs, and POS.	369	171	-	-	100	0
	TOTAL	1583	577				

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Overall percentage

$$\text{Agree} = \frac{2,160}{2,160} \times 100 = 100\%$$

$$\text{Disagree} = \frac{0}{2,160} \times \frac{100}{1} = 0\%$$

4.2. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Data in Table 4.1 above shows the effects of a cashless economy on the performances of small and medium-scale businesses in Abuja, Nigeria. The overall percentage of the respondents who agreed that there are effects of a cashless economy on small and medium-scale businesses is 49.56%. While those respondents who disagreed that there was no effect of cashless on small and medium-scale businesses represented 50.43%. The analysis above indicates the following as the effect of cashless on small and medium-scale businesses.

There were conveniences in electronic transactions such as POS, ATM, Mobile banking, etc. Automatic electronic payments assist in enhancing bank deposits by so doing increasing money available in the banks for businesses to borrow as loans. It is safer and convenient to use electronic payment since it has a huge number of benefits to the economy. A cashless economy eases credit availability. Also, electronic transactions increase the purchasing power of businesses.

Data in Table 4.2 also shows some of the challenges that have hindered the adoption. Overall, the percentage of the respondents who agreed that there are challenges represents 36.68%. Those respondents who disagreed that there are challenges in the adoption of a cashless economy in Abuja represent 63.32%. The analysis above indicates the following as the challenges hindering the adoption of cashless policy in Abuja, to include: lack of awareness, less access to information technology, poor banking habits, online banking frauds, poor power supply, low literacy level, and huge protocols involved in clearing cheques, etc.

Data in Table 4.3 above shows some of the ways that the introduction of the cashless policy enhances the development of the economy. The overall percentage of the respondents who agreed that the introduction of a cashless economy enhances the growth of the economy is 87.65%. Those respondents who disagreed that a cashless economy contributes to the growth of the economy represent 12.34% of the respondents. The analysis above indicates that government support, and creating awareness about banking services will make SMEs productive, and by extension create employment opportunities.

Data in Table 4.4 above shows the way forward out of the identified challenges associated with the adoption of a cashless economy in Abuja. The respondents who agreed that the challenges can be surmounted represent 100%. While those who disagreed represent 0%. The analysis above shows that among others, creating awareness; providing of efficient online network; enacting the right policies, and creating enough payment and online transaction platforms such as ATMs, POS, etc. will go a long way in curbing the identified challenges militating against the effective implementation of the cashless economy policy in Abuja, Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

The introduction of a cashless policy in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja is a welcome development. However, due to the enormous challenges attributed to it, very few small and medium-scale businesses have been able to tap into and take advantage of the cashless economy policy. Also, it is evident that due to poor networks, and low literacy levels in some parts of Abuja, only a very small of small, and medium-scale businesses have started making day-to-day payments and business activities through point-of-sale (POS), mobile Banking, and Automated Teller Machine (ATM)

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the above findings, the study makes the following recommendations;

- 1) Based on the fact that small-scale businesses in Abuja are characterized by a small amount of capital which has consistently hindered the adoption of the cashless policy, it is therefore recommended that the government should embark on viable reforms and financial programs and policies that will make small-scale businesses viable and productive.
- 2) There is a need for small business owners to know, that the government should embark on educating and training members on ICT programs in both urban and rural areas so that small-scale business owners could have the basic knowledge that would enable them to carry out their business activities.
- 3) It is recommended that the government should invest more in information and communication technology to support small and medium-scale enterprises. This will enable them to create jobs for Abuja residents and by extension Nigeria.

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